

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Through the discipline: The effect of motivation on employee performance

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of motivation on employee performance through Discipline. The population of this study were employees of the State Civil Apparatus and Non-State Civil Apparatus of the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of the Bali Province Regional Tax and Retribution Service in Denpasar City. The sampling design uses nonprobability sampling with saturated sample technique that uses all members of the population of 70 employees. Data were collected through questionnaires that were distributed directly and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS). This research is designed quantitatively. The results showed that Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of the Bali Province Regional Tax and Retribution Service in Denpasar city. The results of the analysis show that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The higher the motivation obtained, the higher the employee performance. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Discipline, the higher the motivation the higher the employee's Discipline. Discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, the higher the Discipline, the higher the employee performance.

Keywords: Motivation; Employee Performance; Discipline; Performance; Human Resource

1. Introduction

Human resources are a partner that also determines the growth and development of an organization. In this regard, the classification and quality of human resources determine the quality of service, image and trust which directly effect the level of professionalism which continues at the level of participation in the success of government agencies in achieving their goals.

Nengsih *et al.* (2023) defines employee performance as an overall ability of a person to work in such a way as to achieve optimal work goals and various goals that have been created with sacrifices that are rationally smaller than the results achieved. Sumardika *et al.* (2023) stated that employee performance is a set of results achieved and refers to the achievement and implementation of an individual or group job requested by the supervisor. Hidayat *et al.* (2023) state that performance is the result of employee effort which is effect by abilities and perceptions of roles and tasks. CNBC Indonesia (2023) Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform (PANRB) the quality index of the State Civil Apparatus is still low. The first performance-based transformation, the quality index of the State Civil Apparatus in Indonesia is still low compared to other countries. Therefore, the government encourages transformation in terms of organization, staffing, and work systems in the implementation of bureaucracy in Indonesia. Second, the bureaucracy must have an impact on society by serving the community with excellent service. Third, the bureaucracy is collaborative so that it can realize a better understanding to solve complex problems involving many stakeholders. Performance that is not ego sectoral allows organizational work to be more efficient in creating outcome-based performance. Fourth, service quality development. Such as serving with a smile and acting quickly in handling community needs.

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Ajabar (2020: 45) states that Discipline is a tool used by managers to change a behavior and as an effort to increase a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms. Wijaya (2015: 291) states that Discipline is an attitude of respect, respect, obedience, and obedience to applicable regulations, both written and unwritten and is able to carry them out and does not avoid receiving sanctions if he violates the duties and authority given to him. Keith Davis in Mangkunegara (2020: 129) states that "Discipline is management action to enforce organization standards". It can be interpreted that Discipline is the implementation of management to reinforce organizational guidelines. The results of a pre-survey of employees within the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of the Bali Province Regional Tax and Retribution Service in Denpasar City regarding Discipline, 10 out of 10 interviewees stated the importance of Discipline so that employee performance increases, if a mistake is made by a State Civil Apparatus employee or Non State Civil Apparatus employee violating existing regulations, sanctions will be imposed according to the violation committed, so that the deterrent effect will make all employees more careful at work and can improve employee performance in completing their work.

Kurniawan, (2022) states that Motivation is a set or collection of behaviors that provide the basis for a person to act in a way that is directed towards certain specific goals. Sutrisno, (2019) that motivation is a factor that encourages someone to carry out an activity. Motivation is often defined as driving individual behavior in achieving goals. Judge, (2020) states that motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction, and persistence of individual efforts in achieving goals. Motivation functions as a driving force that effects a person's actions in work and achievement. Lutfi *et al.* (2022) state that Motivation is a state or condition that encourages, stimulates, or moves someone to do something in order to achieve a goal. They also explained that Motivation can be categorized as a force within a person that effects the direction, intensity, and persistence of voluntary behavior. Gustiawati *et al.* (2022) argued that providing motivation to employees aims to increase passion and enthusiasm, morale and job satisfaction, and employee productivity. Manik *et al.* (2023) in their research, motivation is defined as factors that direct and encourage a person's behavior or desire to carry out an activity which is expressed in the form of hard or weak effort.

The results of a pre-survey of employees within the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of the Bali Province Tax and Retribution Service in Denpasar City regarding Motivation 9 out of 10 stated the importance of Motivation to improve employee performance and Discipline because with motivation employees are eager to complete their duties and meet local revenue targets in each quarter. Superiors are expected to provide high motivation to employees so that employees are able to work in accordance with the rules that have been set where they work and also meet low-level needs (physical, security, and social) and high-level needs (prestige and self-actualization) and suggest that the best way to motivate individuals is to meet their high-level needs. Factors such as policies, company administration, and adequate salary in a job will reassure employees, if these factors are adequate then people will be satisfied and employee performance results will be good. However, there are employees who feel that they do not have a very high desire to learn, so employees are unable to master their work.

2. Literature and Hypothesis Development

Hartiningsih (2017) states that motivation has a positive and significant effect on Discipline, strong motivation as an encouragement within employees to do a task as well as possible to achieve employee satisfaction goals so that they can work in a disciplined manner. Tapala (2018) explains that to achieve organizational goals, a good level of discipline and high motivation from superiors are needed to ensure the maintenance of order and smooth implementation of tasks, so that optimal results are obtained. Susanto (2019) Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Discipline, Discipline is needed to foster a sense of awareness or willingness of a person to obey all company rules and applicable norms. Motivation has a significant positive effect on Discipline in the Tanjung Pinang City Civil Service Police Unit (Ahmad yani, 2023)

H1: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Discipline

Sitorus, (2020) motivation is a desire or drive to get results and goals. This motivation affects human behavior, functions as a driving force that makes a person eager to act in a certain way towards optimal results which have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Jhon Fernos, (2022) research at the Ar Risalah Foundation in Padang City shows that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The results of the analysis show that the higher the motivation given to employees, the better their performance. Erwin, (2020) the results of their research show that Motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. Providing the right motivation can increase employee morale, which in turn has a positive impact on their performance. Siti Ismaryanti (2019) states that Motivation has a positive relationship with employee performance, the higher the performance produced in the Depok City Solid Waste Division. Motivation is an important factor that can improve employee performance in the public sector,

so that in the Pelalawan Regency Manpower Office motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Ruslihardy, 2020).

H2: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

Fahmi Susanti *et al.* (2022) in their research, found that Discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this study confirms that a good level of discipline will improve employee performance, so they try to do the job as much as possible. The effect of Discipline on employee performance at the Somambawa Sub-District Office, South Nias Regency can be concluded that good Discipline will result in good employee performance, on the other hand, if Discipline is not good, it will also result in poor performance (Samalua Waoma *et al.*, 2021). Discipline in employees of Perum BULOG Java Regional Division has a positive and significant effect on employee performance because the effectiveness of an organization can only be realized with high Discipline. The test results conducted by (Syarkani, 2017) simultaneously found that the Discipline variable had a significant effect on employee performance at PT Panca Konstruksi in Banjar Regency, the level of discipline has a considerable share in determining the level of employee performance.

H3: Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

Ari Sastra *et al.* (2023) state that increasing the provision of Motivation to employees will increase Discipline at Bintang Super Market Ubud Gianyar, the results of this study mean that the higher the motivation given, the higher the discipline of employees of Bintang Super Market Ubud Gianyar at work and can improve employee performance. Aditya Wijaya, (2021) stated that Discipline has a significant effect on employee performance, the more Discipline is improved, the more employee performance will increase. Motivation has a significant effect on employee performance so it is concluded that the more motivation is increased, the more employee performance will increase so it can be concluded that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through Discipline. Discipline with Motivation has a significant impact on employee performance in Kartasura District by implementing policies related to improving employee performance and providing motivation in improving employee performance (Ifah Lathifah, 2023).

H4: Discipline plays a role in mediating the effect of motivation on employee performance.

3. Methods

This study focuses on the field of human resource management, with the subject of the study being employee performance at the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of Tax and Regional Retribution Services of Bali Province in Denpasar City. The object of the study is the analysis of the effect of motivation on employee performance mediated by Discipline. The dependent variable of this study is employee performance. The independent variable consists of motivation, while the mediating variable is Discipline. The assessment indicators of the research variables, namely employee performance, include indicators of work quality, work quantity, effectiveness, and independence. Discipline includes preventive discipline, corrective discipline, and progressive discipline. Motivation includes Motivation, work achievement, opportunities for advancement, recognition of performance and challenging work. Characteristics of 70 respondents, with a total of 23 State Civil Apparatus and 47 Non-State Civil Apparatus. Employees of the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of Tax and Regional Retribution Services of Bali Province in Denpasar City are dominated by men, 44 men compared to 26 women.

This study is classified into the type of associative research that intends to describe and test the hypothesis of knowing the relationship between two or more variables, namely the relationship between motivation variables and human employee performance variables through Discipline. The indicators of each variable refer to several previous research sources that have been modified to adjust the subjects in this study. The sample collection technique in this study was non-probability sampling, namely purposive sampling with a data collection method in the form of a questionnaire distributed to Civil Servant and Non-Civil Servant employees of the Regional Technical Implementation Unit of Tax and Regional Retribution Services of Bali Province in Denpasar City. This research instrument was tested with validity tests and reliability tests, the data analysis technique used was PLS-based SEM.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The measurement model or outer model is carried out to ensure that the measurements taken are valid and reliable. There are several evaluations used in this measurement model, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability tests.

4.2. Convergent validity

Convergent validity is measured through the outer loading value. The minimum outer loading value used in this study is the outer loading value of 0.50 because it is the initial stage of developing the measurement scale. Items that have an outer loading value of less than 0.50 will be removed from the model. The convergent validity test with the outer loading value of each research variable can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Lower Order

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Lower Order	Result
Performance (Y)	Job Quality (Y1.1)	Y1.1.1	0.775	Valid
		Y1.1.2	0.815	Valid
		Y1.1.3	0.881	Valid
	Job Quantity (Y1.2)	Y1.2.1	0.825	Valid
		Y1.2.2	0.794	Valid
	Effectivity (Y1.3)	Y1.3.1	0.828	Valid
		Y1.3.2	0.847	Valid
	Independence (Y1.4)	Y1.4.1	0.873	Valid
Y1.4.2		0.790	Valid	
Discipline (Z)	Preventive discipline (Z2.1)	Z2.1.1	0.799	Valid
		Z2.1.2	0.828	Valid
		Z2.1.3	0.805	Valid
	Corrective Discipline (Z2.2)	Z2.2.1	0.863	Valid
		Z2.2.2	0.831	Valid
	Progressive Discipline (Z2.3)	Z2.3.1	0.776	Valid
Motivate (X)	Motivate (X.3.1)	X3.1.1	0.916	Valid
	Work performance (X3.2)	X3.2.1	0.851	Valid
	Opportunity To Advance (X3.3)	X3.3.1	0.891	Valid
	Recognition of Performance (X3.4)	X3.4.1	0.908	Valid
	Challenging Job (X3.5)	X3.5.1	0.891	Valid

Primary Data, 2024

Tabel 2 Higher Order

Variable	Dimension	Higher Order	Result
Performance (Y)	Job Quality (Y1.1)	0.970	Valid
	Kuantitas Kerja (Y1.2)	0.903	Valid
	Efektifitas (Y1.3)	0.913	Valid
	Job Quantity (Y1.2)	0.917	Valid
Discipline (Z)	Preventive discipline (Z2.1)	0.968	Valid
	Disiplin Korektif (Z2.2)	0.922	Valid
	Disiplin Progresif (Z2.3)	0.776	Valid
Motivate (X)	Motivate (X.3.1)	0.916	Valid
	Work performance (X3.2)	0.851	Valid
	Opportunity To Advance (X3.3)	0.891	Valid
	Recognition of Performance (X3.4)	0.908	Valid
	Challenging Job (X3.5)	0.891	Valid

Primary Data, 2024

Based on Tables 1 and 2, it is known that all items from the lower order and higher order have shown values (outer loading) of more than 0.50. This means that all of these items can be used to measure variables and have met the convergent validity criteria.

4.3. Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity is related to the principle that different construct measures should not be highly correlated. The discriminant validity test is assessed based on the cross loading of the measurement with its construct. It is said to have discriminant validity if the cross-loading correlation value with its latent variable must be greater than the correlation with other latent variables. The discriminant validity test with the cross-loading value can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Discriminant Validity

Indicator	Discipline (Z)	Performance (Y)	Motivate (X)
X.1.1	0.824	0.894	0.916
X.1.1	0.824	0.894	0.916
X.2.1	0.826	0.803	0.851
X.2.1	0.826	0.803	0.851
X.3.1	0.817	0.827	0.891
X.3.1	0.817	0.827	0.891
X.4.1	0.854	0.824	0.908
X.4.1	0.854	0.824	0.908
X.5.1	0.793	0.837	0.891
X.5.1	0.793	0.837	0.891
Y.1.1	0.740	0.775	0.740
Y.1.1	0.740	0.775	0.740
Y.1.2	0.780	0.815	0.819

Y.1.2	0.780	0.815	0.819
Y.1.3	0.797	0.881	0.802
Y.1.3	0.797	0.881	0.802
Y.2.1	0.804	0.825	0.805
Y.2.1	0.804	0.825	0.805
Y.2.2	0.777	0.794	0.744
Y.2.2	0.777	0.794	0.744
Y.3.1	0.791	0.828	0.734
Y.3.1	0.791	0.828	0.734
Y.3.2	0.752	0.847	0.756
Y.3.2	0.752	0.847	0.756
Y.4.1	0.809	0.873	0.854
Y.4.1	0.809	0.873	0.854
Y.4.2	0.708	0.790	0.719
Y.4.2	0.708	0.790	0.719
Z.1.1	0.799	0.760	0.704
Z.1.1	0.799	0.760	0.704
Z.1.2	0.828	0.777	0.786
Z.1.2	0.828	0.777	0.786
Z.1.3	0.805	0.702	0.735
Z.1.3	0.805	0.702	0.735
Z.2.1	0.863	0.821	0.806
Z.2.1	0.863	0.821	0.806
Z.2.2	0.831	0.777	0.794
Z.2.2	0.831	0.777	0.794
Z.3.1	0.776	0.751	0.696
Z.3.1	0.776	0.751	0.696

Primary Data, 2024

4.4. Composite reliability

In addition to the validity test, a variable reliability test was also conducted, measured by composite reliability. A variable is declared reliable if the composite reliability value is > 0.70 . The composite reliability test can be seen in Table 4 below

Table 4 Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite reliability	Value	Result
Motivate	0.951	0.70	Reliable
Performance	0.951	0.70	Reliable
Discipline	0.923	0.70	Reliable

Primary Data, 2024

Table 4 shows that the composite reliability value of each variable has a value > 0.70. This indicates that all variables in this study meet the reliability requirements.

4.5. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The inner model is conducted to test the structural model of the study that describes the relationship between latent variables in substance. Evaluation of the inner model uses the R-square (R2) value for endogenous constructs and Stone-Geisser Q square for predictive relevance. a) R-square value the calculation of the R-Square (R2) value aims to see the magnitude of the correlation value of the endogenous variables resulting from the PLS estimation on each path. The R-Square (R2) value of each endogenous variable of the study is presented in Table 4.

Table 5 R-square

Construct	R-Square
Discipline	0.851
Performance	0.915

Primary Data, 2024

Table 5 shows that the R-square value of the Discipline variable is 0.851. This can be interpreted that 85.1 percent of the variability of the Discipline construct is explained by the independent variables in the model used, while the remaining 14.9 percent is explained by variables outside the model. Likewise, the Employee Performance variable has an R-square value of 0.915. This means that 91.5 percent of its variability is explained by the independent variables in the model used, while the remaining 8.5 percent is explained by variables outside the model. Measuring how well the observation values are produced by the model and its parameter estimates, it is necessary to calculate Q-square (Q2) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1-R_1^2) (1-R_2^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1-0.851) (1-0.915) \\
 &= 1 - (0.149) (0.085) \\
 &= 1 - 0.0127 \\
 &= 0.9873
 \end{aligned}$$

The results of this calculation show that the Q2 value is 0.9873 which is greater than 0 (0.9873 > 0), so it can be interpreted that the research model is good because it has a relevant predictive value, which is 98.73 percent. This shows that the variation in the Employee Performance variable can be explained by the variables used, namely the Discipline and Motivation variables, while the rest is explained by other variables outside this research model.

4.5.1. Direct effect

This study uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis. The results of the empirical research model analysis were carried out using PLS analysis which can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Path Coefficient

There are two values that must be met in testing the hypothesis, namely the p-value is less than the alpha value of 5% or 0.05 and the t-statistic value must have a value greater than 1.96. The following are the results of the calculation of the significance of each relationship between variables in this study.

Table 6 Direct Effect

	Path Coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
X -> Y	0.503	4.188	0.00	Significant
X -> Z	0.923	38.730	0.00	Significant
Z -> Y	0.472	4.103	0.00	Significant

Primary Data, 2024

The Motivation variable has a Path Coefficient value of 0.503, a t-Statistics value of 4.188, and a p-value of 0.00. Because the p-value is less than 0.05 and the t-Statistics value is more than 1.96, the H1 hypothesis is accepted. This shows that Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. The higher the Motivation, the higher the Employee Performance.

The Motivation variable has a Path Coefficient value of 0.923, a t-Statistics value of 38.730, and a p-value of 0.00. Because the p-value is less than 0.05 and the t-Statistics value is more than 1.96, the H2 hypothesis is accepted. This shows that Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Discipline. The higher the Motivation, the higher the Discipline.

The Discipline variable has a Path Coefficient value of 0.472, a t-Statistics value of 4.103, and a p-value of 0.00. Because the p-value is less than 0.05 and the t-Statistics value is more than 1.96, the H3 hypothesis is accepted. This shows that Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. The higher the Discipline, the higher the Employee Performance.

4.5.2. Indirect Effect

The mediating role of Discipline on the indirect effect of Motivation on Employee Performance is presented in table 7.

Table 7 Indirect Effect

	Path Coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Ket
X -> Z -> Y	0.435	3.883	0,00	Signifikan

Primary Data, 2024

The results of the analysis of the effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Discipline show a Path Coefficient value of 0.435 and a p-value of 0.00 greater than 0.05 ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$), then H4 is accepted. This shows that Discipline can mediate the effect of Motivation on Employee Performance positively and significantly. In determining the mediation effect, this study refers to the stages of mediation testing proposed by Hair et al. (2017: 248). The following explanation regarding the mediation effect is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Mediate Effect

Description:

- P1: Direct effect of X to Z
- P2: Direct effect of Z to Y
- P3: Direct effect of X to Y

Based on the results of the analysis, the direct effect between variables can be seen as follows.

Table 8 Summary Research

Variable	Path Coefficient	p-value
X -> Z	0.503	0.00
Z -> Y	0.923	0.00
X -> Y	0.472	0.00

Primary Data, 2024

- Motivation towards Discipline (X to Z -> P1) has a positive and significant effect (Path Coefficient of 0.503 and p-value of 0.00).
- Discipline towards Employee Performance (Z to Y -> P2) has a positive and significant effect (Path Coefficient of 0.923 and p-value of 0.00).
- Motivation towards Employee Performance (X to Y -> P3) has a positive and significant effect (Path Coefficient of 0.472 and p-value of 0.00).

These results indicate that Discipline mediates the effect of Motivation on Employee Performance partially (complementary partial mediation) because P1, P2, and P3 as a whole have positive and significant values. Based on the results of the mediation test, H4 is accepted, namely Discipline is able to mediate the effect of Motivation on Employee Performance.

5. Conclusion

Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance and can encourage employees to behave outside formal duties for the achievement of the organization. Herzberg's theory regarding the theory of motivator factors or motivation that organizations need to create a work environment that allows employees to feel achievement and gain recognition. This can be done through career development, training, and giving more responsibility to employees with the aim that without a salary increase or employee benefits must be motivated towards their superiors to achieve the expected performance. Regarding hygiene factors, the theoretical implications of hygiene factors indicate that although improving working conditions does not directly increase motivation, dissatisfaction can be avoided by meeting needs such as salary increases, improving comfortable and comfortable working conditions and clear and fair organizational policies. Therefore, management must ensure that all aspects of hygiene are met to create a stable work environment. In addition, motivation has been shown to have a positive effect on Discipline, which reinforces the importance of a close relationship between leaders and subordinates. Effective narcissistic leaders can use their charisma to improve the quality of Discipline. This study also found that Discipline has a positive effect on employee performance, emphasizing the need for a mutually supportive relationship to encourage more contributions from subordinates. Discipline serves as an important mediator in explaining how motivation affects employee performance. The quality of the relationship between leaders and subordinates is key to maximizing the positive effect of motivation on employee performance behavior.

Managerial Implication

Research shows that motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance, so organizations need to leverage motivation to improve employee behavior. Managers and leaders should use their charisma and authority to inspire and encourage employee engagement. In addition, motivation also affects Discipline, which emphasizes the importance of the relationship between leaders and subordinates. Organizations should provide interpersonal training and constructive feedback to maintain the quality of Discipline.

Improving the quality of Discipline is essential to driving employee performance, through steps such as mentoring programs and leadership training. Finally, Discipline acts as a mediator that links motivation to employee performance, so organizations need to focus on developing strong relationships between leaders and subordinates through team training and open communication. Thus, these strategies can help maximize the positive effects of motivation on employee performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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